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4th B&H Water Congress

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19. i 20. novembar 2024.
November 19-20th 2024

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SADRŽAJ

/

CONTENT

Napredak u tretmanu otpadnih voda – podrška modelu kružnog upravljanja

Advancement in wastewater treatment - supporting circular management model

A. Leovac Maćerak

D. Žmukić

N. Duduković

N. Slijepčević

A. Kulić Mandić

D. Tomašević Pilipović

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U ovom radu su prikazani rezultati istraživanja rađeni pod okriljem Horizont Evropa projekta pod nazivom „Wastewater Management in Circular Economy Frame (SmartWaterTwin)“ koji predstavlja prvi korak Srbije u upravljanju otpadnim vodom u okvirima cirkularne ekonomije. Sektor voda u zemljama Zapadnog Balkana je trenutno suočen za raznim izazovima pogoršanim klimatskim promjenama i zagađenjem. Otpadne vode mogu poslužiti kao inovativno rešenje koje doprinosi povezivanju vode, energije i povrata materijala. Fokus istraživanja je usmeren ka elektrohemijskim tretmanima kao inovativnim tehnologijama tretmana otpadnih voda i rekuperacije vrednih materijala (fosfora, azota) iz otpadne vode. Predtretmani, uz pomoć „zelenijih“, održivijih, manje agresivnih solventata, pre anaerobne digestije mulja su pokazali da imaju dvostruko dejstvo: smanjenje količine mulja i povećanje produkcije biogasa. Ponovno korišćenje i valorizacija otpadnih voda ima dodatnu korist od smanjenja uticaja na životnu sredinu, do izdvajanja vrednih materija, utičući na smanjenje njihove eksploatacije iz prirodnih izvora, čuvajući rezerve za budućnost.

Ključne riječi

Otpadna voda, komunalni mulj, cirkularna ekonomija

This paper presents the results of the research carried out under the auspices of the Horizon Europe project called "Waste Water Management in Circular Economy Frame (SmartWaterTwin)", which represents Serbia's first step in wastewater management within the framework of the circular economy. The water sector in the countries of the Western Balkans is currently facing various challenges exacerbated by climate change and pollution. Wastewater can serve as an innovative solution that contributes to the connection of water, energy and material recovery.

The focus of the research is directed towards electrochemical treatments as innovative technologies for waste water treatment and recovery of valuable materials (phosphorus, nitrogen) from waste water. Pre-treatments, with the help of "greener", more sustainable, less aggressive solvents, before anaerobic digestion of sludge have been shown to have a double effect: reducing the amount of sludge and increasing biogas production. The reuse and valorization of wastewater has the additional benefit of reducing the impact on the environment, to extracting valuable substances, affecting the reduction of their exploitation from natural sources, preserving reserves for the future.

Key words

Wastewater, sewage sludge, circular economy

Growing freshwater shortage is a worldwide issue. The worldwide water issue is currently the fourth most dangerous risk in terms of its potential to affect society, according to the World Economic Forum. Concerns about the potential effects on human health, the environment, and the global economy are being raised by a notable decline in the quality and quantity of fresh water that is now accessible.

By 2050 more than half the world's population will be at risk of water stress. Rapid urbanization, especially in low- and middle-income countries, has created various water-related challenges. These include degraded water quality and inadequate water supply and sanitation infrastructure. According to Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport (An Economic and Investment Plan for the Western Balkans (Brussels, 6.10.2020 COM(2020) 641 final [1,2]. Western Balkans is projected to be severely hit by climate change. European Innovation Partnerships (EIPs): EIP Water identified the following priority areas: (1) Water reuse and recycling; (2) Water and wastewater treatment, including recovery of resources; (3) Water-energy nexus; (4) Flood and drought risk management; and (5) Ecosystem services. In response to climate change, increasing resource scarcity, and environmental degradation, societies around the world are driving the transition towards the 'circular economy' that focuses on reducing material consumption, reusing materials, and recovering materials from waste. In the

context of water resources management, water utilities are beginning to promote the circular water economy that reduces water consumption, reuses and recycles water and wastewater, and recovers materials, including heat and minerals, from water and wastewater to not only mitigate greenhouse gas emissions but also enhance resilience to climate change.

Furthermore, the United Nations (UN) ranked "Clean Water and Sanitation" as the sixth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to be accomplished by 2030 after acknowledging the significance and urgency of mitigating the freshwater problem. As a result, improving water quality, wastewater treatment, and safe reuse is Target 6.

According to the UN, achieving Target 6.3—one of the eight objectives needed to reach SDG goal 6—is represented by the four actions listed below:

1. Reducing pollution
2. Avoiding dumping and reducing the release of chemicals and hazardous materials
3. Reducing the amount of untreated wastewater by 50%
4. An important global increase in safe reuse and recycling.

It is clear that urban societies and developing industries are the driving forces behind the global economic development. However, ignoring the environmental effects of improper waste treatment and disposal may eventually burden the global economy and lead to the collapse of sustainable ecosystems, which may eventually have an effect on climate change.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are adding a new dimension to the challenges faced in the water supply and sanitation sector, by focusing on sustainability. The investment needed in the water supply and sanitation sector are very large, and as cities continue to grow, there is an opportunity to ensure that investments are made in the most sustainable and efficient way possible. Improvement of existing systems are needed toward innovative treatment solutions and smart management practices. Furthermore, urban development requires approaches that minimize resource consumption and focus on resource recovery, following principles of the

circular economy. By adopting circular economy principles in the processing of wastewater is that resource recovery and reuse could transform sanitation from a costly

service to a self-sustaining and value-adding system. The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans [3], through its pillars, addresses the initiatives to support the region in developing circular economy strategies and fighting pollution of air, water and soil. It further states that WB region has only basic sanitary facilities and wastewater collection, while urban areas with collection of wastewater via sewer networks discharge mostly untreated wastewater. In Republic of Serbia, only 1.7% of wastewater per capita is treated. RS still has an engineering approach to wastewater treatment design versus river basin level one. Great investment are expected in this sector and knowledge-based solutions are necessary. The need to improve knowledge generation and dissemination, facilitating access to knowledge and the exchange of good practices in water management sector is evident in Western Balkan region. European Green Deal⁴ emphasizes the support of less developed regions and European Commission (EC) seeks to harmonize the situation at European level so that there are no such differences in individual countries and even regions – „Leaving no one behind“. An increased support needs to be allocated to less developed regions. The EC emphasis also the importance of sustainable management of water and wastewater as one of the elements in the transition towards the circular economy. Balkan is lagging several decades and is still on level of harmonizing Water Framework Directive in national legislative. Additionally, water developed European countries are far ahead and changing water management towards sustainability. It is important to act now and to intercept current knowledge and experiences of developed countries to be able to keep up in this sector in the future. Action is needed toward stepping up to international cooperation and collaboration in science, research and innovation for the sustainable development of water resources at the local, national and regional levels, including through

public-private and multi-stakeholder partnerships, and on the basis of joint interest, mutual benefit and common future.

1. Wastewater treatment

It is essential to understand that the contaminants found in wastewater differ in composition and concentration based on where they originate when considering wastewater treatment. Therefore, carefully considering and selecting appropriate treatment methods and steps are necessary to ensure the treated wastewater is safe for discharge into aquatic systems or soil. Over the past two decades, several water treatment methods have been employed to treat wastewater for reuse. These methods encompass chemical precipitation, membrane based-treatments, coagulation and flocculation, filtration, adsorption, ion exchange and biological treatment methods [4]. Nevertheless, biological processes can produce undesirable byproducts and frequently require for precise control over operating conditions, longer treatment times, and larger physical footprints. However, chemical processes require a lot of chemical inputs, which raises total costs and makes downstream processes more difficult, which might result in secondary pollution. Additionally, membrane filtration and adsorption, unless complemented by comprehensive pre-treatment processes, gradually lose efficiency over time due to pore blockage by pollutants and reduced flux (the flow rate of treated effluent per unit surface area). Electrocoagulation may be used to treat a variety of wastewaters, including industrial, agricultural, and municipal wastewaters, in contrast to large-scale biological treatment, which has limited capacity to handle wastewaters with high toxicity, xenobiotic chemicals, and pH and needs certain circumstances. Due to its versatility, ease of set-up, in-situ coagulants produced during treatment, and lack of chemical addition requirements, electro-

coagulation could be used very successfully for small-scale, decentralized municipal domestic sewage treatment.

Studies on LCA as an estimating and decision-making tool that take particular local criteria into account are few, particularly in developing nations. In addition to aiding in the selection of the best possible treatment alternatives, life cycle assessment (LCA) would highlight the areas of the chosen technology that require more improvement and optimization [5]. The wastewater sector's sustainable growth depends on the environmental effect and cost evaluation components, which also offer suggestions for future legislation and the water sector. In addition, the circular economy concept suggests a novel approach to conventional WWTP that is promoted to address important sustainability concerns such emissions, chemical use, water and energy dependency, and the growing volumes of leftovers following wastewater treatment. Adopting this strategy might transform an existing WWTP into a "biofactory" that improves the quality of discharged water while enabling the recovery of materials, energy, and—most importantly—water, all of which become resources.

According to Leovac Maćerak et al (2024) [6]., their study is the first one which used certain quantitative approaches (such as life cycle assessment) to examine the potential of electrocoagulation as a municipal wastewater treatment technology. This study assessed electrocoagulation for the treatment of real municipal wastewater with the inclusion of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) for assessing its environmental performance. The experimental details are explained in the paper [6].

A schematic representation of a batch EC reactor is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a batch EC reactor [6]

For the purposes of this research, eight sets of experiments were performed with monopolar (MP) and bipolar (BP) arrangement electrodes: (1) Al(-)/Al(+), (2) Fe(-)/Fe(+), (3) Fe(-)/Al(+), (4) Al(-)/Fe(+), (5) Fe(-)/Al/Al/Fe(+), (6) Al(-)/Fe/Fe/Al(+), (7) Fe(-)/Fe/Fe/Fe(+), (8) Al(-)/Al/Al/Al(+).

After completion of 8 sets of EC experiments, the most successful arrangement was chosen based on the highest removal efficiencies. Considering that the price of the treatment increases: (1) with the reaction

time, authors examined the influence of time on the efficiency of the treatment and (2) with increasing current intensity - a low current (2.33 mA/cm²) to the selected treatment was applied.

The bipolar arrangement of Al(-)/Al/Al/Al(+) electrodes displayed removal efficiencies in compliance with national regulations (Official Gazette of the RS, 67/11, 48/12, 1/16). To assess the environmental impact of its use in wastewater treatment, LCIA was applied to a bipolar arrangement of Al(-)/Al/Al/Al(+) electrodes, assuming a lower current density of 2.33 mA/cm² and a response time of 30 minutes. LCIA discovered that the EC

method considerably lowers freshwater and marine eutrophication by effectively removing phosphorus and nitrogen from wastewater effluent. It also reduces toxicity to marine and freshwater habitats. However, in all other effect categories examined in this study (global warming, fossil fuel usage, human toxicity, acidification, and terrestrial ecotoxicity), the EC process had a greater influence. These findings are clarified by the properties of the EC process, which allows contaminants extracted from effluent to stay in the environment and eventually accumulate in precipitate. The pollutants in precipitate, spread as sludge, will ultimately find their way into agricultural soils. Furthermore, the process's high energy demand, as well as the assumption that raw sludge is scattered on agricultural land with no pre-treatment or material recovery, contribute to these results.

LCIA analysis indicated that main focus for technology improvement in this regard should include alternative, renewable, energy sources and replacement of conventional electrode materials with more environmental friendly ones.

As water scarcity represents the biggest global challenge, primarily because millions of people around the planet do not have access to clean water, about 70-75% of the world's water consumption is used for agricultural irrigation. In order to meet the needs for fresh water, it is necessary to consider alternative water resources, which will primarily be able to be used for agricultural purposes. Purified municipal wastewater is considered an environmentally friendly option for irrigation of agricultural areas. Many studies emphasize the benefit of applying purified municipal wastewater, which is reflected in the reduction of the need for fertilizer, because purified municipal wastewater contains nutrients and organic matter available for plants. Different technologies are applied for municipal wa-

stewater treatment in different parts of the world. Depending on the development of the country, purified wastewater is obtained as a product. The application of insufficiently purified municipal wastewater, which in terms of chemical and microbiological quality represents a risk, causes the accumulation of chemical and microbiological polluting substances in the soil, which affects the properties of the soil, and then productivity and fertility. Also, pollutants can enter the food chain through crops irrigated with insufficiently treated municipal wastewater, posing a direct threat to the health of farmers and consumers. Therefore, for the application of treated wastewater, all risks must be at an acceptable level.

In the paper of Duduković et al. (2024)[7]., the potential of treated wastewater as a resource for irrigation in agriculture was examined, after the applied bipolar electrocoagulation treatment. In order to assess the quality of purified wastewater, the obtained values of chemical and microbiological parameters were compared with national and international regulations.

Based on the comparison of the obtained results according to the national regulation (Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, 23/94), the water quality after the bipolar electrokinetic treatment showed satisfactory quality, which means that it can be used for irrigation. According to Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on minimum requirements for water reuse, 2020/741, food crops that are consumed raw, but only those parts that are not in direct contact with treated wastewater, and non-food crops, including crops that are used to feed animals that produce meat and milk (class B). An additional assessment, based on the total mineralization of the water, as well as the content and ratio of concentrations of Na, Ca, K and Mg, also determined that the water

quality is acceptable for irrigation, but it is recommended to use this water for irrigating soils with good water permeability. Based on all of the above, we can conclude that treated wastewater can be a potential resource in agriculture.

In addition to, Leovac Maćerak et al. (2023) [8]., made an attempt to close-the-loop in wastewater treatment, by recycling its own sludge (through generated catalyst) in the wastewater line, polluted with recalcitrant organic compounds. Additionally, wastewater treatment process residues were further characterized in terms of elucidating nutrient-release content and the potential to act as soil amendments enforcing a zero-waste principle. The scheme of the process is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of the phases of the conducted experiments (1. Pyrolysis, 2. Synthesis of nZVI-BC; 3. nZVI-BC application as Fenton catalyst; 4. ignition of Fenton sludge (FS) to form FStreated; 5. FStreated application as Fenton catalyst; 6. FS application in nutrient release experiments after ignition [8].

Sewage sludge may be used to produce biochar in wastewater treatment plants. This material, when combined with an external iron supply, can be utilized as a carbon-iron composite to treat a variety of organic contaminants in advanced oxidation processes. Authors used [8] “green” synthesized nano zero-valent iron (nZVI) supported on sewage

sludge-based biochar (BC)-nZVI-BC in the Fenton process for the degradation of the recalcitrant organic molecule. In this way, the circular economy concepts were supported inside wastewater treatment with immediate loop closure. Unlike prior articles, which solely evaluated water treatment, the authors offered a new method to wastewater treatment, including solutions for both water and sludge. nZVI-BC was used in the Fenton treatment for the degradation of Reactive Blue 4, a model substance containing a complex and stable anthraquinone structure. The definitive screening design model proposes a high dye-removal efficiency of 95.02% under the following optimal conditions: [RB4] = 50 mg/L, [nZVI] = 200 mg/L, [H₂O₂] = 10 mM. pH correction was not performed (pH = 3.2). Afterwards, the remaining Fenton sludge, which was thermally treated (named FStreated), was applied as a heterogeneous catalyst under the same optimal conditions with a near-complete organic molecule degradation (99.56% ± 0.15). It could be clearly noticed that the cumulative amount of released nutrients significantly increased with the number of leaching experiments. The highest cumulative amounts of released K, Ca, Mg, Na, and P were therefore observed at the fifth leaching cycle (6.40, 1.66, 1.12, 0.62, 0.48 and 58.2 mg/g, respectively). According to the nutrient release and toxic metal content, FStreated proved to be viable for agricultural applications; these findings illustrated that the “green” synthesis of nZVI-BC not only provides innovative and efficient Fenton catalysts, but also constitutes a novel approach for the utilization of sewage sludge, supporting overall process sustainability.

2. Sewage sludge as a resource

The circular economy idea indicates a novel approach to traditional wastewater treatment facilities, which is advocated to solve critical sustainability components such as

emissions, chemical consumption, water and energy dependency, and rising volumes of post-treatment wastes or bio-solids. Sludge is an organic substrate relatively rich in nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), as well as trace elements. The composition of sludge varies regionally and seasonally, but there is limited data on its nutrient content. It is estimated that about 2.3-3.1 Mt of nitrogen and about 0.23 Mt of phosphorus are found in the sludge generated during one year in the world. Sludge produced from treatment of domestic sewage has long been applied to agriculture as a source of nutrients to displace mineral fertilizers. Kerkez et al (2024) [9] conducted excessive literature review in order to access the sludge management practices in Europe. In addition, nutrient potential in sludge was evaluated on a national level. Major opportunities and challenges were identified. According to authors data, 27% of produced sludge in Europe is used in agriculture as fertilizer on arable land and pastures. This method is dominant in Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Spain and Sweden. Composting and similar uses: use of waste sludge after mixing with other organic material and composting, followed by use for parks and gardens takes about 21%. This method is dominant in Cyprus, Estonia, France, Hungary, Luxembourg and Slovakia. According to national Sludge Management Program, in Republic of Serbia around 135 000 tons of dry matter of sludge can be expected in the future. This represents the source of nitrogen and phosphorus in amount of over 4500 tons each. On the other hand, concerns arise from the possibility of the presence of various emerging contaminants. However, these risks should be viewed rationally in relation to the characteristics of the wastewater entering the plant, as well as through the efficiency and type of applied technologies in the water line, which is closely related to the quality of the separated sludge. Authors pointed that con-

trolling the users of the sewage system and optimizing the operation of the wastewater treatment plant, these risks can be reduced to a minimum. Furthermore, more efficient technologies to preserve extract and reuse nutrients from sewage sludge can be used. By Kerkez et al. (2024) [9], states need to recognize the real value of wastewater and the potential resources that can be recovered from it. It includes resource recovery and general circular economy principles within their strategies, investment planning and infrastructure design.

One of the technology used for emphasis on energy conservation and recovery and desire to obtain beneficial use of sewage sludge is anaerobic digestion. Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a cost-effective and easy process for reducing sludge pollution and converting organic fractions into value-added products. Sludge pretreatment prior to anaerobic fermentation is crucial for accelerating sludge hydrolysis and removing competing inhibitors. In the study of Leovac Maćerak et al (2024) [10], authors employed acetic acid as a non-aggressive acid, to directly treat sewage sludge in batch AD experiments. The objective was to evaluate the production of biogas from anaerobic digestion (AD) using raw sludge as substrate and supernatant after AD as inoculum, both taken from WWTP of nominal capacity of 150 000 equivalent per capita (EC). The total solids (TS) content of the raw sludge was 4.35%, and the volatile solids (VS) accounted for 74% (w/w) of TS. The evaluation of the methane production potential was performed in a bench-scale experiment using the biochemical methane potential (BMP) test in mesophilic conditions. The inoculum-to-substrate ratio used was 2:1. The dosages of acetic acid were in the range of 1 mM – 5 mM. The BMP tests lasted 10 days. Results showed that biogas production of AD batches with acetic acid pretreatment at 4 mM and 5 mM on AD were effectively

enhanced, with the highest production being 2.7 and 3.6 times of that observed in control AD without acetic acid treatment. However, the AD batches with acetic acid treatment at low dosages of 1-3 mM had lower methane production (~1.5 times). The average VS removal effectiveness of 33% indicates a reduction of VS in the analyzed treatment. Total and soluble carbohydrates were consumed in AD process with an average percentage respectively of 74%-84%, while breakdown of total proteins concentration reach about of 40% at the highest dosage. Results show that acetic acid significantly promotes sludge disruption and increases dissolved material quantities and enhances the degradation and conversion of macromolecular organic matter (e.g., proteins and polysaccharides). The obtained results have to be considered as preliminary data to point out main characteristics and the anaerobic biodegradability of pre-treated sewage sludge.

By far, a number of materials and products have been found and recovered from the wastewater. Cellulose is one of the components that may be recovered from sewage water, along with phosphorus and ammonium. Cellulose contributes significantly to chemical oxygen demand (COD) and suspended solids (SS) in municipal WWTP influents. A large fraction of this cellulosic matter is recalcitrant to current physicochemical and biological treatment technologies, resulting in extra surplus sludge production. Fine sieves are a viable alternative to primary clarifiers, primarily collecting cellulosic components from wastewater. They produce a fibrous mass with 70% cellulose content, a renewable ingredient in green goods manufacturing. This fiber can be used in various sectors, including paper, construction, furniture, textiles, automotive, and bioethanol and bioplastics. Leovac Maćerak et al (2024) [11], investigated recuperation of cellulose fibers from primary sewage sludge and homogenized sludge

before entering anaerobic digester. For the main sludge, a typical cellulose extraction technique with two NaOH extraction steps and one bleaching step was adequate to remove the sludge and the majority of the color. Furthermore, heating with deionized water reduced turbidity and produced a layer of foam, indicating fat removal. In contrast, following the first alkaline treatment (2 wt% NaOH), homogenized sludge samples remained viscous, with dark-brownish fibers. This was resolved by treatments with higher NaOH concentrations (4 wt%). After that step, the resultant pulp was identical to that generated from primary sludge. After the treatments, the cellulose content of primary sludge was around 22%, while homogenized sludge contained only 8%. The variation in cellulosic content in sewage sludge samples can be a consequence of pre-treatment, human activity etc. A simple approach for extracting and determining cellulose content in primary sludge and homogenized sludge was presented. The approach relies on alkaline and bleaching treatments. Cellulose content in wastewater varies a lot and further investigation should be pointed on other sources in wastewater treatment plant for its recovery. Also, new "recovery facilities" have the potential to practice recovery. Recovered cellulose is valued and regarded a valuable product, because it can reduce aeration cost, waste sludge quantity and/or chemical consumption.

Duduković et al., 2024 [12], investigated phosphorous recovery by electrochemical precipitation process, using synthetic sample reflecting the anaerobic digester supernatant with phosphorous and nitrogen concentration of 121 mg/L and 737 mg/L, respectively. Subsequently, electrochemically induced struvite precipitation was conducted utilizing magnesium electrodes. In this way, the method used introduces a new way of sourcing magnesium, decreasing dependence on chemical

additives for struvite formation. The results obtained reveal complete removal of P across all tested pH levels (7.5, 8, 9, 10). However, N content decreases progressively with higher pH values; for instance, at pH10, 55% less N was detected compared to the initial level (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Efficient removal of N and P after EK treatment

Additionally, Slijepčević et al. (2024) [13] investigated the potential of recycling sewage sludge using the process of stabilization and solidification (S/S). Waste sludge generated from WWTPs or ash after incineration poses significant environmental challenges due to its high organic content and potential for contamination. However, through S/S technique, this research explores methods to stabilize the sludge or ash and transform it into a safe and usable construction materials, for land reclamation, and other applications.

3. Conclusion

Electrochemical technologies have drawn a lot of interest lately because of their capacity to use a variety of factors to achieve effective performance. These cutting-edge techniques have shown remarkable efficacy in eliminating persistent organic contaminants from wastewater and preventing environmental damage. Among the electrochemical processes, EC has emerged as a widely used and promising technology for cost-effective and efficient treatment of water and wastewater, while minimizing sludge production.

It offers flexibility, ease of use, and the ability to handle various contaminants

Purified wastewater after applied EC treatment showed potential for irrigation in agriculture, taking all risks at acceptable levels.

Recycling sewage sludge, is crucial for reaching carbon neutrality in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Sewage sludge could be used as resource of many value-added products, for instance nutrients, biogas, cellulose etc.

A circular economy-based approach enables minimized water resource consumption, and maximized wastewater reuse and recycling, while promoting concentrated material recovery at all stages of the traditional approach is encouraged.

LITERATURE

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